

**IMPORTANCE AND DEVELOPMENT OF INTERNET
MARKETING**

FOR ENTERPRISES IN THE B2B MARKET

*Kayimova Z.A - Associate Professor,
Department of Economics, BukhSU*
*Umarova Kh., 2nd year master's degree
"Digital Economy" BukhSU*
*Zhuraeva R - 2nd year master's degree
"Digital Economy" BukhSU*

Abstract: the Internet has become a powerful marketing tool for sales, communications and market analysis of B2B companies. To correctly assess the results of a company's activities on the Internet, it is necessary to introduce an Internet marketing complex into the company's unified marketing information system.

Key words: Internet, B2B, Internet marketing, website, e-mail marketing, advertising campaign, strategy, marketing communications.

Marketing theory developed by considering the relationship between the seller and the consumer in the B2C market (business-to-customers, "business for the consumer"). The rules and laws formulated during this time can also be applied to the B2B (business-to-business) segment. However, marketing activities in the B2B sphere are very specific and have a number of significant differences. Having gone from a simple information repository to an effective sales and analysis tool, the Internet has taken a significant place in modern life and made a real revolution in marketing.

Erasing time and geographic boundaries, the Internet has become a platform on which companies can directly interact with consumers of their products. Thanks to the Internet, a new direction has emerged - Internet marketing,

which includes a set of various tools (Internet marketing complex). Today, not a single enterprise can afford to ignore the achievements of information technology development, since this will lead to significant financial losses.

Companies operating in the corporate sector are no exception. At the same time, Internet marketing in the B2B sector is a relatively new phenomenon, little studied and requiring comprehension and systematic research. The B2B market is characterized by the need to build long-term marketing relationships with the channel. It is characterized by large volumes of purchases, narrow market segments, rational consumer behavior, a long sales cycle, a complex purchasing process in which a wide range of people participate. The most significant forms of marketing communications in the corporate sector are personal selling and sales promotion, advertising and PR should be developed taking into account the principles of content marketing.

However, the maximum effect is achieved when using integrated marketing communications, when each form complements each other. According to the results of the study, both heads of industrial enterprises and companies, and specialists in the field of Internet marketing unambiguously called the website the main, integrating marketing tool. This is also explained by the fact that a well-designed website allows you to solve several marketing problems (from consumer research , understanding the communication impact and directly converting contact with the site into an order or purchase.

Using the site allows you to improve the quality and availability of the service: for example, materials on the company's website are available 24 hours a day, 7 days a week. But the most important advantage of the site is that if it is built correctly, it is able to integrate all elements of the marketing complex (product and service policy, pricing, promotion and sales, as well as staff work).

In this regard, Internet marketing in an industrial company should always begin with a website and a significant part of resources and efforts should be concentrated on working with it, since the very fact of having a website does not

always allow solving problems companies both in terms of attracting new clients and in terms of translation contacts in transactions. In order for the site to fully perform all marketing functions, it needs support from other online marketing tools. In this regard, let us note the fundamental points that should be taken into account when developing Internet marketing programs for industrial companies:

1. Changes in consumer attitudes towards communications. According to Kim Larson, international director of Google BrandLab, the majority of consumers (including industrial ones) have little trust in “official” communications from the company itself, and are more inclined to believe information from the same consumers or other independent sources. In particular, she says: “Instead of telling your story through video, invite users to participate in its creation.”[2].

Therefore, news sites, professional forums and even social networks must necessarily be included in the communication channels of an industrial company, since news and any other information from these sources will be considered more reliable and trustworthy (especially if the news resource or forum makes it possible to generate and view “feedback” with other consumers). The company, of course, may face difficulties in managing these uncontrolled communications, especially if it has previously used only its controlled channels. However, this is not a reason to refuse to use social networks, forums and other professional sites, but rather an opportunity for appropriate adjustments to marketing activities.

2. Rapid growth in the number of industrial companies with their own website. Commercial users of the Internet are the fastest growing part of it, and the presence of a company’s website is no longer its absolute competitive advantage, but rather, the absence of a website automatically excludes the company from the competition rent struggle.

3. The company and its website must be supported not only by company employees, but also by constant communications with consumers.

4. In industrial marketing, good optimization for search engines, as well as regular updating of information on the website allows you to save money on the

production of expensive printed products and quick updates provide the necessary information.

5. Numerous opportunities that are provided by just one registration procedure on the site: conducting a customer survey, organizing personalized e-mail mailings taking into account the interests of a particular group of potential customers. consumers without significant costs, introduction of loyalty programs (establishment of special discounts for registered users).

To increase the effectiveness of Internet marketing programs in industrial companies, it is worth paying attention not only to those tools that are most interesting and convenient for the company, but also to those that are interesting to the buyer (i.e. they want to solve his problems in the best way). It is worth noting that an industrial company can achieve significant dividends from Internet promotion only through joint use of its website and a complex of additional tools for its promotion for the purposes of group of consumers and experts.

In addition, modern effective marketing in the B2B sphere also involves the integration of online and offline tools, since it is mainly the company's employees who serve customers and close transactions. Therefore, the expansion of the activity of an industrial company on the Internet must necessarily be accompanied by adequate organizational changes in the company.

Summarizing the above, it can be noted that in order to increase the effectiveness of Internet marketing programs in industrial companies, it is worth paying attention not only to those tools that are the most interesting and convenient for the company, but also those that are interesting to the buyer (i.e., allow him to solve his problems with the best way).

LITERATURE

1. Giyazova, N. B., Bakayeva, M. A., & Giyazov, B. B. (2022). Public Financial Control Policy And Its Theoretical Foundations. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 128-130.

2. Hakimovna, U. M., & Muhammedrisaevna, T. M. S. (2022). The Role Of Banking And Accounting In The Development Of Small Business And Entrepreneurship. *International Journal Of Social Science & Interdisciplinary Research* Issn: 2277-3630 Impact Factor: 7.429, 11, 136-143.
3. Furqatovna, O. N., Niyozovna, N. I., & Nutfulloyevna, A. H. (2022). Approaches Aimed At Ensuring A High Quality Of Education In The Training Of Economists. *Journal Of Ethics And Diversity In International Communication*, 2(3), 78-83.
4. Dustova, A. K. (2022). Mechanisms For Development Of The Region And Tourism In Foreign Countries. *Инновационные Исследования В Науке*, 1(14), 121-124.
5. Muminov, K. I., & Abdullaeva, H. (2020). The Effect Of Coronavirus Pandemic To Uzbekistan Tourism. *South Asian Journal Of Marketing & Management Research*, 10(11), 36-42.
6. Abdullayeva, H. (2021). Japanese Experience In Increasing The Efficiency Of Tourist Territories In Uzbekistan. *Центр Научных Публикаций (Buxdu. Uz)*, 7(7).
7. Abdullayeva, H. (2022). Analysis Of Economic Development Of Tourism During Pandemy. *Центр Научных Публикаций (Buxdu. Uz)*, 22(22).
8. Nutfilloyevna, A. H. (2022). The Main Factors Of Economic Development Of The Tourism Industry. *European Multidisciplinary Journal Of Modern Science*, 4, 627-631.
9. Hakimovna, U. M. (2022). The Importance And Analysis Of The Accounting Department Of Enterprises And Its Management. *European Multidisciplinary Journal Of Modern Science*, 4, 834-837.
10. Sharopova, N. (2019). Analysis of parents' satisfaction with pre-school education in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, 10(9), 829-840.

11. Nematilloevna, K. N., Salimovna, N. G., & Muxammedovna, T. M. (2021). Genesis Of The Essential Content Of The Hotel Service As An Object Of Consumer-Oriented Marketing. *Academic Journal Of Digital Economics And Stability*, 12, 54-62.
12. Sharopova, N. (2021). Marketing strategies for the development of the market of preschool education services in Uzbekistan. *Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities*, 1(1.1 Economical sciences).
13. Niyozova, I. (2021). The Transition To The Green Economy And The Importance Of Strategy. *Центр Научных Публикаций (Buxdu. Uz)*, 8(8).
14. Navruz-Zoda, L. B., & Navruz-Zoda, Z. B. (2020). Improvement Of Social Prestige Of Entrepreneurial Companies In Bukhara Region. *Academy*, (3), 37-39.
15. Usmanova, A. B. (2022). Sport Tourism As A Sport And Form Of Activity. *European Journal Of Innovation In Nonformal Education*, 2(1), 212-214.
16. Abdullajanova, D. S. (2023). Socio-psychological criteria for the selection and placement of personnel in management (on the example of women). *Confrencea*, 5(05), 401-411.
17. Усманова, А. (2022). The Current State And Analysis Of The Tourist Potential Of The Bukhara Region. *Центр Научных Публикаций (Buxdu. Uz)*, 15(15).
18. Akhmedova, Z. (2022). Development Of Active And Passive Vocabulary In Preschool Children With Motor Alalia Using Art Therapy Elements. *Ann. For. Res*, 65(1), 7148-7161.
19. Akhmadjonova, S., & Abdullajanova, D. (2023, May). SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF FAMILY CONFLICT RESOLUTION. In *Academic International Conference on Multi-Disciplinary Studies and Education* (Vol. 1, No. 6, pp. 101-108).

20. Narzullayeva, G. S., & Bakayeva, M. A. (2022). Creative Management: Creative Opportunities In Business Process Management. *American Journal Of Social And Humanitarian Research*, 3(12), 58-63.

21. Mukhamedova, D. G., & Abdullajanova, D. S. (2020). The actuality of the gender aspect of the manager's constructive interaction in the conflicting situation. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(12), 228-231.

22. Mukhamedova, D., Abdullajanova, D., Tukhtabekov, K., Fuzailova, G., Babadjanova, S., & Rahmonova, Z. (2019). The main directions of accounting socio-psychological characteristics of the manager of education in the process of optimizing management activities in Uzbekistan. *Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems*, 11(10 Special Issue), 1035-1038.

23. Odinayeva, N. F., Bakayeva, M. A., & Giyazov, B. B. (2022). Intellectuals With Higher Education In The Economy And Ways To Increase Their Competitiveness. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 84-86.

